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Staff Performance And Organizational Non-Financial Motivation In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, non-financial motivation plays a significant role in enhancing staff performance and organizational effectiveness. While financial rewards are important, non-financial incentives like recognition and job security significantly impact staff satisfaction and productivity. Implementing strategies such as structured recognition programs, promoting work-life balance, and providing opportunities for growth can boost staff moral and contribute to a more productive workforce. This paper became necessary to determine other non-financial staff motivation in Nigeria and how it impacts on employees' performance. Secondary sources of data collection was adopted. Again, qualitative-descriptive and explanatory research methods was employed. We recommended among others that the management must ensure that the organizational leadership should adopt a good leadership style that will go a long way to inspire and motivate employees to achieve a successful organizational goal. Again Workers participation or involvement in decision making in order to increase the level of sense of belonging to workers motivate organizational staff.

Keywords: Staff Performance, Non-Finical Motivation, Workers, Organizational Goal

INTRODUCTION

Employee's motivation is the most driving force that engenders the morale and performance of workers in organization. This is because, existence of low motivation leads to low job satisfaction, increases intention to quit or job turnover (low commitment), and other negative work-related behavior. In the same vein, the presence of increased motivation breeds high commitment, job satisfaction and other positive job related behavior for ensuring organizational development.

Employee motivation has been at the fore front of research for over many decades and continues to generate interest amongst academics and practitioners because of the changing structure of work attributable to globalization, the change in society and work demography (Ehimen, Mordi & Ajonbadi, 2014). Researchers have spent many time and resources in research towards identifying the several techniques of motivating employees for optimum performance (Abasilim & Ubani, 2014). However; different employees are motivated differently with varied type of motivation to achieve high performance and objectives of the organization. Apart from financial incentives, non-financial strategies such as praise, promotion, employee recognition, and office environment have significant effect on employees' performance in the transmission company of Nigeria (Oigbochie, Ajalie, & Okwara, 2024).

Public Administrators and managers have put more efforts in finding the proper application of motivational process to achieve high performance of workers for organizational productivity. Although it has been observed that most managers mainly rely on the use of financial motivation as the core means of motivating workers (Nosiri, 2013). Many scholars believed that financial incentives (motivation) cannot be able to motivate workers in organization in some circumstances. For example Job security is another

significant non-financial incentive, particularly relevant in the public sector, where employees may place a high value on long-term stability. Job security enhances loyalty and reduces turnover intentions, creating a stable workforce essential for institutional knowledge retention (Okeke-Uzodike et al., 2022). Therefore non-financial motivation also play a significant role in motivating workers for high performance (Griffin & Moorhead, 2007; Kreitner & Kinicki, 2004; Nosiri, 2013).

Over the years it has been assumed that the ineffectiveness of public services in Nigeria is associated with the issue of poor motivation of workers. The problem of achieving adequate motivation in Nigerian public service has generated a lot of negative work-related behaviours like absenteeism, organizational conflict, employer-employee disharmony, lateness to work, low commitment, poor performance, corrupt practices etc, which set to undermine the success of the public service. These issues raise the question of emphasizing on the use of non-financial motivation to increase workers performance. Again given the socio-economic pressures faced by public servants, particularly in regions with high inflation and limited private sector alternatives, effective non-financial reward programs can play a pivotal role in retaining skilled personnel (Agbo, 2023).

It is against this backdrop that this work is set to critically evaluate staff performance and organizational non-financial motivation in Nigerian public service.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

1. Motivation: Motivation in this work simply means the forces or the act of stimulating workers to take or perform certain action towards achieving organizational goals.

2. Non-Financial Motivation: This is motivation that does not involve monetary or financial incentives (money). Here this research will focus on the following indices like, good leadership, workers involvement/ participation, recognition, job enrichment, promotion, training, office facilities, effective communication and discipline.

3. Performance: behaviors or actions of employees that contribute either positively or negatively towards the achievement of organizational goals

MOTIVATION

According to Samson and Daft (2003), Motivation as the “forces either within and external to a person that arouse enthusiasm and persistence to pursue a certain course of action.” This implies that motivation can come from external and internal factors, Greenberg and Baron (2000) viewed that motivation comprises of three main components which include “first, arousal that deals with drive, or energy behind individual(s) action. Second, meaning the choice people make and the direction of their behaviour tasks and the third parts, deals with maintaining behaviour, showing how persistent people move to achieve such goal.”

Robbins (2001) sees motivation as “the process that account for individual’s intensity, direction and persistence of efforts towards attaining a goal.” In the same vein, Kue and Byara 1986 (as cited in Nosiri, 2013) argued that motivation include three characteristics. “First motivation is concerned with what activates human behaviour. Second, motivation is concerned with what directs this behaviour and third motivation is concerned with how behaviour is sustained.” In addition, Lathan and Pinder (as cited in Colquitt etal, 2011) sees motivation as set of energetic forces that originates both within and outside an employee, initiates work-related efforts and determines its direction, intensity and persistence. This illustrates that motivation does not only involves one factor rather it comprises of distinct forces which constitutes internal and external which ensures direction, intensity and persistence of efforts towards achieving a goal (Nosiri, 2013).

Furthermore, Sharma and Sadana (2010) see motivation as “the inner force that moves the people to work.” Similarly, Terry and Franklin (1982) viewed motivation as “the need or drive within an individual that drives him or her towards goal oriented action.” This shows that motivation comes within the individual or people to satisfy a need in organization (Nosiri, 2013).

Kelly 1974 (as cited in Nosiri, 2013) defined motivation as “behaviour instigated by needs and directed towards the goal that can satisfy these needs. This means that those needs which an individual experience are what motivate him to take a course of action to achieve a goals. Similarly, Griffin and Moorhead (2007) looked at the understanding of motivation on need deficiencies. They viewed that “motivated behaviour normally starts when a person has one or more important needs because unmet needs leads to more intense feelings and behavioural changes and a need deficiency usually triggers search for ways to satisfy it.” In addition, Weihrich and Koontz (1994) see motivation as comprises of chain reaction. They viewed that “felt needs give rise to wants or goals sought, which causes tensions (that is unfulfilled desires) which give rise to actions towards achieving goals which finally result in satisfaction.” This implies that the needs must be unsatisfied because if the needs are satisfied, such needs cannot be seen as motivating force or drive.

In aspect of achievement of goals, Griffin and Moorhead (2007) see motivation as a goal-directed behavior. In the same vein, Agulanna and Awuji (2005) viewed that “motivating people is about getting them to move in the direction you want them to go in order to achieve a goal. Motivating oneself is again about setting the direction independently and then taking the necessary measures to ensure that you get there.” In addition Chung (as cited in Terry and Franklin, 1982) looked at motivation as a goal directed behaviour which is characterized by the process of selecting and directing certain actions among voluntary activities to achieve goals.” This shows that motivation directs human behaviour towards achieving a goal.

LeMay (2002) brought another different perspective on motivation by defining motivation as “all the factors of the working environment that have any positive or negative effects on an individual’s work.” This shows that motivation include negative aspect. Hick 1970 (as cited in Nosiri, 2013), looked at motivation as the use of punishment, sanction, disciplinary measures. Therefore negative motivation which is called the stick approach made use of threat or punishment to boost workers morale.

PERFORMANCE

Performance is regarded as the record of outcomes achieved. On an individual basis, it is a record of the person’s accomplishment. Bernadin, Kane, Ross, Spina and Johnson 1995 (as cited in Adeoti & Isiaka, 2006) see performance as “the outcomes of work because they provide the strongest linkage to the strategic goals of the organization, customer satisfaction and economic construction.” This means that performance is as a result of work done. In the same vein, Campell 1990 (as cited in Abdullah & Wan, 2013) see performance as “behavior demonstrated or something done by the employee for organizational performance outcome, turn over, sales volume, income and declared shareholders dividend, and the quality as well as quantity of service.”

Ezigbo and Timinepere (2011) define performance as “what an employee does or does not do. Employee performance common to most jobs include the element of output, timelines of output, presence of work and cooperativeness.” Furthermore, Rashidpoor (as cited in Abasilim & Ubani, 2014) defined performance as the set of behaviour which a person shows in relation his job or in other words, amount of efficiency gained due to the person’s job type.” Campell (as cited in Colquitt et al, 2011) defined performance ‘as the value of set of employees’ behaviour that contributes either positively or negatively to organizational goal accomplishment.” This means that performance can be either positive or negative.

Griffin and Moorhead 1995 (as cited in Nosiri, 2013) viewed performance as made up of all or totality of work-related behavior. This means that, any behaviour that is not relevant to an organization cannot be regarded as organizational or employees’ performance.

Brumbach 1988 (as cited in Adeoti & Isiaka, 2006) asserted that performance “means both behaviours and results. Behaviours emanate from the performer and transform performance from abstraction to action. Not just the instruments for results, behaviours are also outcomes in their own right, that is, the product of mental and physical effort applied to tasks that can be judged apart from results.”

Jones, George and Hill study 2006 (as cited in Ezigbo & Timinepere, 2011) posited that organizational performance is a measure of how effectively and efficiently managers use resources to satisfy customers

and achieve organizational goals. They further say that organizational performance increase in direct proportion to increase in efficiency and effectiveness.

Also, Colquitt et al (2011) identified three categories of behaviours as relevant to performance which include: task performance, citizenship behavior and counterproductive behaviour. This means that both task performance and citizenship behavior contribute positively to organizational goal accomplishment while counterproductive behavior contributes negatively to organizational goal accomplishment (Nosiri, 2013).

EMPIRICAL ASSESSMENT OF STAFF PERFORMANCE AND NON-FINANCIAL MOTIVATION IN NIGERIA.

Scholars such as Anyim, Odogwu and Badejo, (2012) looked at the motivation and employee's performance in both public and private sectors in Nigeria. They asserted that there are certain factors that could guarantee or enhance employees' performance which include: good leadership, catering for the interest of workers, good working conditions, periodic job training, team building, good interpersonal relationship, management of conflict, participatory management, presence of good pay. So they concluded that in order to elicit better performance, motivational factors must be accorded high priority and employed properly as an essential ingredient for organizational progress and survival especially in the current day turbulent operating environment.

Abasili and Ubani (2014) made an empirical synthesis of employees' perceived relationship between motivation and job performance in Abia State Civil Service. They found out that there is significant positive relationship between motivation and employees job performance; there is a significant positive relationship between intrinsic motivation and job performance and there is a significant positive relationship between extrinsic motivation and job performance in Abia State Civil Service. They further recommended that organizational leaders in Abia State Civil Service should learn about what their employees want from their jobs to determine the appropriate techniques to use to motivate workers properly.

Zameer, Ali, Nisar and Amir (2014) critically examined the impact of the motivation on the employee's performance in Beverage Industry of Pakistan. They observed that there is a significant relationship between motivation and employee's performance in Beverage Industry of Pakistan. Therefore, the motivations in Beverage Industry of Pakistan can significantly influence performance of employees.

Opu (2008) studied motivation and work performance in Kitgum District Local Government of Uganda and discovered that there has been considerable success in the use of both the hygiene factors and motivators. That is hygiene factors like, working conditions, work relations, physical environment, supervision and job security should be able to form the base line that can stimulate the motivators like achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement and training to motivate work force adequately.

Idemobi, Onyeizugbe and Akpunonu (2011) investigated the compensation management and organizational performance in Anambra State Civil Service. They discovered that financial compensation for staff members in the public service do not have a significant effect on their performance and that financial compensation received are not commensurate with staff efforts. And the reform programmes of the government do not have a significant effect on the financial compensation policies and practices in the public sector due to poor compensation management. They further recommended for adequate design of financial compensation that will link with performance.

Adeoye and Elegunde, (2014) examined the compensation management and motivation for organizational performance. They maintained that there is a relationship compensation management, motivation and organizational performance. So they further argued that for any organization to be highly competitive and productive, it needs adequate compensation management and motivational process or factors which must be in place for the benefit of both employees and organization.

Osa (2014) looked at the monetary incentives on organizational performance and argued that monetary motivation or incentives is a good motivational tool on employee performance in a society like Nigeria since there is presence of increase in population of people that experienced low standard of living.

However, he added that money is not the only sufficient incentives to motivate workers. He suggested that organization should ensure that their employees are well remunerated in line with an economic environment and there is need for employment of various techniques to motivate workers.

Hosain (2014) critically examined the impact of financial and non-financial rewards and employee empowerment on task motivation and from performance of line employees of Bangladesh. Hosain maintained that feedback and rewards affect the scope of empowerment in a different way for lower level managers in different industrial sectors of Bangladesh than they do for top level managers. Furthermore, financial feedback has a significant and positive effect on perceived impact while performance based rewards have little significant and negative effects as self-determination and perceived competence and only greater levels of perceived impact were associated with greater motivation. He further viewed that firms should consider carefully the techniques they apply to increase feelings of empowerment among non-management employees.

Nosiri (2008) studied motivation and productivity in to Imo State Civil Service. He discovered that there are presence of problem of regular promotion, ineffective flow of communication, poor psychological working conditions, authoritarian leadership style, poor disciplinary measures, excessive organizational conflict, poor training, poor remunerations, etc, which lowered the level of worker morale or motivation towards achieving organizational goals and productivity in Imo State Civil Service. Therefore, it means that workers are not adequately motivated in Imo State Civil Service. He further recommended for adequate provision of regular promotion, remuneration, encouragement of participatory management, delegation of authority/ functions, regular training and application of appropriate disciplinary measures in Imo State Civil Service and Nigerian Civil Service at large.

Lameck (2011) critically studied the non-financial motivation and performance of police headquarters in Tanzania. He discovered that the perception of police officers at Tanzania Police Force Headquarter are that the use of non-monetary incentives especially social and job-related is not at the adequate levels in the organization and the employees viewed that non-monetary incentives is the most important factor that increase their morale and efforts to perform well.

Ezigbo and Timinepere (2011) examined the effects of monetary and non-monetary rewards on the employees' performance in manufacturing firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. They discovered that monetary and non-monetary rewards had significant positive effects on employees' performance in the selected firm in Rivers State. They further concluded that monetary and non-monetary rewards should be provided in manufacturing settings to engender employee behaviour for performance at the individual and organizational levels.

Adeoti and Isiaka (2006) critically investigated the impact non-financial compensation on employee performance in selected Nigerian firms. They discovered that majority of the firms possess non-financial packages. And the present non-financial compensation leads to improvement to employees' performance in the selected firms. Also the job itself and job environments serves as the most important factor of non-financial compensation. They further recommended that there should be employment of friendlier climate in the firms and the work environment should be made conducive.

Nosiri (2013) critically studied the non-financial motivation and workers performance in Imo State Civil Service and discovered that the achievement of high performance is more of a question of non-financial motivation than financial motivation; that there is a significant relationship between non-financial motivation and employees' performance in Imo State Civil Service. He recommended that there is need for encouragement of employee involvement or participation in decision making, recognition of employee efforts, appropriate job design, regular training of staff etc.

Ameh and Shokumbi (2013) looked at the extent of effectiveness of non-financial motivational scheme on construction workers output in Nigeria. They discovered that the most effective non-financial motivation to skilled and semi-skilled workers include provision of personal protective equipment, love and belongingness, leadership by example, free transportation and free medical facilities. And the most effective non-financial motivation to management staff include provision of residential accommodation, company car with free fuel allocation, pension scheme and opportunity to do something. Therefore, this

shows that there is a difference between the non-financial techniques that motivate non-managerial and managerial staff in construction firms in Nigeria.

Yousaf, Latif, Aslam and Saddiqui (2014) investigated the impact of financial and non-financial rewards on employees in Pakistan. They discovered that between financial and non-financial rewards, the financial rewards are more important for employee motivation in the third world countries like Pakistan because of the high rate of inflation that made people to struggle to retard their social status. This means that appropriate motivational techniques depend on the economic circumstance of a country. In similar vein, Harunavamire and Kanengoni (2013) investigated the influence of monetary and non-monetary rewards on motivation of lower level employees in selected retail shops. They revealed that there is no significant effect of monetary rewards on employee motivation, non-monetary rewards have a significant effect on lower-level employee motivation and recognition is the best motivating factor for lower level employees. In all cases, demographic variables like gender, and occupation played a significant role in the relationship between rewards and motivation.

Welhrick and Knootz (1994) viewed that money is very important in motivating employees towards achieving high performance. They also believe that if money is to be effective motivator people in various positions must be given salaries and bonus that reflect their individual performance. Therefore, this view implies that for money to serve as a good motivator it must reflect the individual performance of employees.

Money can therefore provide positive motivation in the right circumstance not only because people need and want but also because it serves as highly tangible means of recognition. This shows that satisfaction of various needs of individuals need to play a significant role. Meaning that, any type of motivation needs money as its backbone. In the same vein, Stoner and Freeman (cited in Nosiri, 2013) argued that money is the obvious and frequently used incentive but not the only means of motivating workers.

Mathaur and Imhoff (2006, p.3) posit that “increase salaries are by no means sufficient to solve the problem of low motivation. More money does not automatically imply high motivation. We therefore suggest that any comprehensive strategy to maximize health workers. Motivation in a developing country context has to involve a mix of financial and non-financial incentives.” This means that both financial and non-financial factor can motivate workers. That is emphasis should be based on both money and other incentives towards motivating workers for high performance. Furthermore, Mullins (2005) says that motivation is about much more than money.

According to Horick (cited in Mullins 2005) “as I thought about this, I decided that motivation was not just about money. It was about creating an environment which people enjoyed working.” Therefore, money is not the sole motivator for high productivity and performance.

Looking at the aspect of measures that need to motivate employee, Chukwudum (2010, p.19) studied the Nigeria schools and identified the measures to use to motivate workers which include:

1. Adequate and timely payment of workers salary and issuing of merited compensation.
2. Improved approval or leave (annual or sabbatical leave for staff)
3. Creating conducive atmosphere for positive social interaction and relaxation.
4. Creating a clear and operational channel of communication
5. Praising and encouraging workers
6. Providing the necessary equipment, materials and conductions.
7. Should delegate his duties were possible etc.

In addition, fox (cited in Nosiri, 2013) identifies the strategies on how a boss can motivate employees to work effectively these includes: “tell the people what needs to be done; tell the people why it is needed; have chosen to do it, train the people; remove frustration and barriers that fetter the people; inspect progress and; say thank you” publicly and privately.”

This shows that good manager must not rely only on one technique towards motivating workers. There is need for delegation of powers, training of staff, effective communication, involvement of employee in decision making, provision of physical working equipment etc.

In looking at leadership LeMay (2002, p.227) took another approach and sees leadership as a source of motivation. He argued that a leader is concerned about the quality of face supervision, tangible benefits and incentives and using the intrinsic interest of task to motivate employees. This means that effective leadership (mainly democratic leadership) can motivate employee in organization.

Robbins (2001) looked at the case of communication and sees communication as a factor of motivating workers. He stated that communication fosters motivation by clarifying to employees what is to be done, how they are doing and can be done to improve performance. In the same vein, Ogunna (2004) views that motivating device include socio-psychological factors such as applying well chosen, articulated communication skills to stimulate the workers, encouraging and appealing to the workers and mobilizing the workers to achieve a desired goals.

One of the primary function of communication in an organization is to achieve mutual understanding thereby help establish the social condition which will motivate the employee (Ogunna, 1999). This view above indicates that poor communication leads to problem of motivation among workers which has resulted to low performance of workers.

Looking at the issue of participatory management or employee involvement in decision making, Kreitner and Kinicki (2004, p.389) argued that participation management is predicted to increase motivation because it helps employees fulfill three basic needs.

1. Autonomy
2. Meaningfulness of the work
3. Interpersonal contact.

Again, Gibson et al (1994, p.170) supported the importance of participation as a motivational. He argued that empirical evidence suggests that a number of organizational and personal benefits can result from participation when properly applied; it is effective in improving performance, productivity and job satisfaction. This implies that participation or involvement of employees in organizational activities creates a strong feelings of trust to the management, enhance harmony, employee support and cooperation which will produce employee participation will engender high motivation in an organization (Nosiri, 2013).

CONCLUSION

Staff motivation is highly essential for the success of any organization because it determines the rate of employees' performance. And the issue of performance is not only a question of only financial or monetary motivation or incentives but requires the application of non-financial aspect of incentives or motivation. (Nosiri, 2013; Mullins, 2005). This means that despite the crucial role of monetary motivation towards achieving positive performance, non-financial motivation sometimes plays a greater role in motivating workers.

This work revealed that non-financial motivation has a significant relationship with workers performance in Nigeria. However, it revealed that there is poor application of non-financial motivation which undermines the performance of workers. These were as a result of poor leadership style, problem of participatory management / low involvement, poor physical working conditions, poor communications etc.

Therefore, to achieve high rate of motivation among employees for positive performance in Nigeria, there is need to not only rely on financial motivation rather, emphasis should look at non-financial aspect of motivation in order to achieve organizational success.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Workers participation or involvement in decision making in order to increase the level of sense of belonging to workers motivate organizational staff.

Again, workers recognition: That is, emphasis must be based on recognition programmes which must have link with workers performance. Also, the management should ensure regular promotion of workers,

to enable staff have faith with their organization and put more effort. Furthermore, management must ensure that the organizational leadership should adopt a good leadership style that will go a long way to inspire and motivate employees to achieve a successful goal. Also, there is need for adequate application of disciplinary measures on workers. This will help to control any negative work-related behaviors among workers.

Finally, there is an urgent need for the management to provide adequate physical working conditions like office facilities and equipment in order to boost workers morale. This is because poor facilities can discourage or reduce the morale of workers in an organization.

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